

Understanding Bipolar Disorder Psychopathology from a Socioecological Perspective

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Abstract

The biology of bipolar disorder psychopathology has been studied extensively since Emil Kraepelin published his famous psychiatric nosology at the start of the twentieth century. Bipolar illness psychopathology is highly impacted by complex bidirectional relationships between individual, interpersonal, environmental, societal, and historical factors, according to new studies. To systematically study these relationships and their impact on the etiology, expression, and treatment of bipolar disorder psychopathology, this review employs Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory and Process-Person-Context-Time model. This approach is supported by conceptual, theoretical, and empirical research. Future research and implications for mental health practitioners are also explored.

Keywords: Brain hacking • Psychopathology • Bipolar disorders • Ecological systems theory • Bipolar spectrum

Introduction

Bipolar disorders are a diagnostic category characterized by mood swings of different intensity that occur on a regular basis [1]. Signs of mania (e.g., flight of ideas, increased goal-directed behavior, decreased desire for sleep, impulsivity), hypomania (e.g., milder symptoms of mania), or depression can all occur throughout an episode (e.g., feelings of worthlessness, suicidal ideation, psychomotor agitation, anhedonia). Recurrent episodes vary in length and can include traits such as anxious distress or a mixed state in which manic and depressed symptoms are present at the same time. Bipolar illnesses can strike at any time in life, but the majority of instances appear in early adulthood. Comorbidity, suicide risk, and hospitalization have all been proven to be major predictors of early onset, manic episodes, and episodes with mixed features in particular [2-5]. Patients with bipolar illnesses are believed to be 15 times more prone than the general population to attempt suicide, and up to 30% of all cases show serious impairment in school, job, and/or home. Patients with bipolar disorder experience symptoms even when they are not experiencing an episode. Symptoms of diseases reduce overall functioning [6-8]. The significance of heredity in the development of bipolar disorders, as well as the advantages of genetic testing It has long been understood that medication can be used to treat them. While there is a lot of in these areas, there is still much to learn, as research in recent years has revealed. Psychological, social, and environmental processes were also investigated. Engaged in the genesis, manifestation of symptoms, and treatment adherence and bipolar disorder prognosis.

Ecological systems theory and the PPCT model characteristics

The ecological systems theory and, by extension, the PPCT model are both based on this idea that individuals have one-of-a-kind, bidirectional interactions. Their immediate surroundings, society as a whole, and historical events are all important to them. A person's behavior, psychology, and pathology are constantly influenced over one's lifetime

[9-10]. To put it another way, human development is defined as a process that effects both individuals and groups. Generations after generations these concepts are deeply established in psychology's understanding of human development is based on a large number of sources a series of sophisticated theoretical conversations about growth itself Methodologies for measuring relevant research that should be used conceptions, as well as the waves of empirical evidence that follow.

Theory of ecological systems

The ecological systems theory is divided into five layers, each of which is nested within the others and influences the others in a bidirectional manner. The microsystem, the mesosystem, the ecosystem, and the macrosystem are all parts of the same system as well as the chronosystem. A microsystem is made up of a human, their environment, and their environment's environment local surroundings, as well as other contexts in which they are directly involved take part in (for example, in home, school, and/or job). The development of a country is heavily reliant on reciprocal trades. In such situations, family members and peers are important. In this case, a person assumes different personas based on who and what they are confronted with, and these personas shape an individual over time as personal relationships develop. Others build relationships with you, and you seek to introduce them to others. Complicated stimuli and help to develop a person's cognitive, Development on all levels: physical, social, moral, and emotional.

PPCT model

The PPCT model investigates four key properties that influence each of the ecological systems theory's levels: proximal processes, people, context, and time are all factors to consider. Bronfenbrenner and his colleagues refer to proximal processes are long-term interactions between two or more entities. As the "core" of these models, there is an individual and an environment. Genotype expression is shaped by proximal processes, which lead to the realizing one's potential to comprehend oneself and the world, maintain self-control, cope with stress in a healthy way, and learn efficiently build and maintain solid bonds, and take an active role in their surroundings Proximal processes differ greatly from one person to the next. Individuals, but they can also involve parental ties, playing alone or with others. friends, acquiring new skills, participating in sporting activities, and caring for others some other person. Stable mesosystems are required for the success of proximal processes; otherwise, the developing individual will be unable to proceed toward increasingly complex interactions, stagnating and eventually dying potentially suffer from pathology-especially if they've been abused or neglect. According to the PPCT model, individual attributes have a significant impact. Proximal processes are influenced. The way one feels (e.g., temperament), demand characteristics and bio-ecological resources (e.g., intellect) (For example, age) can direct growth in a disruptive way, such as through apathy and indifference generatively, by interest and attentiveness, or distractibility. Context encompasses factual facts, emotional experiences, and personal experiences. As a direct effect of one's actions, one's beliefs and motivating variables grow. environment. The term "time" relates to a person's level of involvement. long-term activities and connections, and societal issues during an activity as well as cultural shifts that occur before or throughout one's lifetime.

Bronfenbrenner's approach to bipolar disorder

Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory and PPCT model are especially useful in comprehending the complexities of bipolar illness genesis, symptom expression, treatment adherence, and prognosis. Based on current conceptual, theoretical, and empirical literature, the following sections will use these frameworks to develop an ecological map of the diversity of bipolar illnesses among individuals.

Future research and implications for mental health professionals

Person traits influence the strength and direction of proximal processes across all subsystems of the ecological systems theory, which

in turn shape person characteristics and developmental outcomes that either persist or change over time. These bidirectional environments and interactions determine the etiology of bipolar disorders, and their manifestation is infinitely modified by them-especially if they are unstable and incapable of supplying cognitive, moral, social, physical, and behavioral nutrition. These changeable aspects must be taken into account on a case-by-case basis to adequately evaluate the demands and problems of individuals with bipolar illnesses. The ecological map given in this paper could help mental health clinicians and researchers better understand and direct their work.

Fostering the well-being of these patients, for example, at the microsystem level entails detecting risk factors like early onset and working quickly to establish a link between the patient, their family, and the healthcare system. Family members can help discover joyful (hypo) manic symptoms that would otherwise go unnoticed by older individuals. Patients with bipolar illnesses should be offered empathy and proper information of their condition at the microsystem level, as well, to improve treatment adherence and cultivate resilience elements. Genetic counselling and other forms of therapy at the micro- and meso-ecosystem levels would underline the importance of such risk factors and encourage family members to seek treatment for their own mental health issues. Communication between different types of mental health practitioners is critical at the macro system level to ensure that patients with symptoms of varying severity be treated, whether they are in the midst of an episode or not. Short gaps between episodes and relapse in general, as well as major concerns connected with severe episodes such as suicide and hospitalization, may be reduced with consistent follow-up. Future study should continue to explore bipolar spectrum concepts at the chronosystem level, with the goal of implementing novel diagnostic criteria, healthcare training programs, and treatment approaches that fully include the variability of this group. Mental health practitioners should recognize that the symptoms of a depressed episode and major depressive disorder are the same, based on current criteria and knowledge of bipolar illnesses. As a result, both diagnosis should be considered equally. Overall, mental health practitioners and academics should be conscious of their enormous and critical role in not just treating but also influencing bipolar diseases.

Conclusion

To the author's knowledge, this is the first review to apply Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory and PPCT model to the psychopathology of bipolar disorder. These frameworks contribute to the

development of an ecological map of bipolar disorder etiology, expression, and treatment results, which was presented in this review through conceptual, theoretical, and empirical research. Overall, this study implies that the procedures utilized to treat people with bipolar illnesses should be reconsidered from both a holistic and person-centered approach. The author hopes that this study will assist mental health professionals and researchers in better understanding this complicated diagnostic category and how patients' lives are affected by a variety of events.

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